

A Life Threatening Stridor Due to Huge Retrosternal Goitre: A Case Report

Dr. Abbas A.R. Mohamed ✉

Consultant general and laparoscopic surgeon King Salman Specialty Hospital, Hail, Kingdom of Saudi Arabia

Dr. Saud Rashidi

Consultant head and neck and endocrine surgeon Security forces hospital al Riyadh, Kingdom of Saudi Arabia

Dr. Abdulaziz M. Almotlag

Consultant general, laparoscopic and metabolic surgeon King Salman Specialty Hospital, Hail, Kingdom of Saudi Arabia

Dr. Abdulla E. Alshamari

Consultant general and laparoscopic surgeon King Salman Specialty Hospital, Hail, Kingdom of Saudi Arabia

Dr. Ibrahim Alrashidi

Consultant diagnostic and therapeutic radiology King Salman Specialty Hospital, Hail, Kingdom of Saudi Arabia

Abstract

A retrosternal goiter, also known as a substernal gaiter, is an enlarged thyroid gland that grows downwards and extends through the thoracic inlet into the thoracic cavity. We present a case of retrosternal goiter that presented with recurrent attacks of breathlessness and was misdiagnosed as bronchial asthma for years and treated with steroids and bronchodilators. The patient presented with inspiratory stridor and the diagnosis was confirmed by a CT scan of the neck and chest. Total thyroidectomy was performed through a cervical approach and the stridor disappeared completely after surgery.

Introduction

The normal anatomical position of the thyroid gland is in the anterior part of the neck, behind the strap muscles and around the cricoid cartilage and the tracheal rings. A retrosternal goitre is generally defined as a thyroid mass in which 50% or more of its volume is located below the thoracic inlet. We report the case of a 53-year-old woman who presented with shortness of breath and stridor. A CT scan of the chest revealed a marked enlargement of the thyroid gland with an extensive intrathoracic component completely encircling part of the intrathoracic trachea causing severe stenosis. She underwent urgent thyroidectomy without sternotomy, with complete resolution of symptoms immediately after surgery.

Case Report

A 53-year-old woman presented to our emergency department with progressive inspiratory stridor that

had persisted for 5 days. She had been suffering from recurrent attacks of shortness of breath for three years and was diagnosed with bronchial asthma and treated with steroids and bronchodilator inhalers. She is neither diabetic nor hypertensive and has had no previous surgery.

On examination, she was obese with a body mass index of 42 and was anxious with audible inspiratory stridor and expiratory wheezing. Respiratory rate was 24 per minute and oxygen saturation was 93% on room air. Auscultation of the chest revealed wheezing on both sides of the chest and inspiratory stridor. Examination of the neck revealed a fullness on both sides of the midline with no other abnormalities.

Her blood tests, including thyroid function test, complete blood count, coagulation test, serum calcium and urea, creatinine and electrolytes were within normal limits [Table 1]. X-ray of the chest showed subepiglottic narrowing of the trachea extending to the level of the cornea [Figure 1].

More Information

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Table 1: Showing the Results of Blood Tests

Haemoglobin	of 13.3 g%	12-16g%
White blood cell	9,00/mm ³	4,000-10.500/mm ³
Platelet	273,000/mm ³	150-450/mm ³
INR	1.25	0.9-1.1
APTT	of 10.60s	10.1-12.8
GLUCOSE RANDOM	56.9 mmol/L	4.1-7.1 mmol/L
BUN	3.8 mmol/L	3.2-8.2 mmol/L
CREATININE	84 mmol/L	100mmol/L
CALCIUM	2.43	2.08-2.65 mmol/L
T3	3.2	2.3-4.2 pg/ml
T4	1.73	0.89-1.78 ng/dl
TSH	4.9	0.55-4.78 mIU/L

Figure 1: Chest X-ray showing narrowing of the trachea extending from level of thoracic inlet (white arrow) to the level of the tracheal bifurcation (yellow arrow)

A CT scan of the neck and chest revealed a large goiter with retrosternal extension causing significant narrowing of the trachea [Figure 2]. The goiter is about 2.5 cm long and is located 3.5 cm below the vocal cords; it shows calcifications with some cystic changes. The left lobe measures 6.4 x 3 cm, the right lobe 8 x 3.3 cm. The tracheal wall thickening is preserved. There is no significant cervical or mediastinal lymphadenopathy, apart from a few small pre-tracheal lymph nodes. The laryngeal skeleton is intact with no glottis, subglottic or supraglottic masses.

She was discussed by a multidisciplinary team including a specialist in endocrine surgery, endocrine medicine, thoracic surgery, radiology and an anaesthesia, who decided on urgent surgery through a neck incision with the possibility of a sternotomy. The patient was operated on the next day after three units of blood had been cross matched, and informed consent had been obtained. No difficulties were encountered during intubation.

Figure 2: The Neck and Chest CT Scan [Axial Cuts] Showing the Tracheal Compression at Cervical Region [figure A] and at the Thoracic Inlet [figure B]

Figure 3: The Neck and Chest CT Scan [Coronary Cuts] showing the Cervical Part [figure A], And the Intrathoracic Part [figure B] of the Goiter

Figure 4: The Neck and Chest CT Scan [Sagittal Cuts], Figure A Showing Both Cervical and Thoracic Extension of the Goiter [Yellow Arrow], and Figure Showing the Relation of the Goitre to the Aortic Arch [Green Arrow].

The operation was started with a cervical collar incision. The upper poles of both lobes were mobilized by ligation and division of the superior thyroid arteries on both sides, preserving the external branches of the superior laryngeal nerves. The retrosternal part of the gland was delivered from the chest without a sternotomy. The inferior thyroid arteries were ligated and divided with the aid of a nerve stimulator, preserving the inferior thyroid nerves and the parathyroid glands. The patient was ex-tubated immediately after surgery without having respiratory distress. She was admitted to the intensive care unit for 24 hours for observation. Her vital signs remained stable, and she was transferred to the general ward the next day. Serum calcium levels and thyroid function tests remained within normal limits postoperatively.

She was discharged on the third postoperative day on 100ug of levothyroxine daily and calcium and vitamin D supplement.

Discussion

The term "goiter" is derived from the Latin "tumid um gutter" – swollen Bneck – and is described as a thyroid gland that is double or more the normal size or over 40 g weigh [1].1 The term retrosternal goiter is not yet uniformly defined in the literature, nor is the part of the thyroid gland that protrudes or descends from the neck into the thorax [2]. However, the most commonly accepted definitions describe a retrosternal goiter as a goiter that has descended below the level of the thoracic inlet or whose mass is more than 50% below the thoracic inlet [3-5]. Retrosternal goiter is classified as a primary or secondary goiter depending on where it

originates. Primary retrosternal goiter is caused by ectopic thyroid tissue in the mediastinum and is supplied with blood by the intrathoracic arteries instead of the thyroid arteries. A secondary retrosternal goiter is defined as a goiter that has descended from the neck to below the thoracic inlet, or a goiter whose mass is more than 50% below the thoracic inlet. Huins and colleagues [6] proposed a further classification of retrosternal goiter based on the anatomical extent of thyroid enlargement into the thoracic cavity. They divided retrosternal goiter into three groups and proposed an optimal surgical approach for thyroidectomy: (1) a thyroid gland in which part of the gland protrudes below the thoracic inlet when the patient is in the surgical position; (2) a gland that reaches the level of the aortic arch; (3) a thyroid gland that reaches the level of T4 [on the chest radiograph]. The prevalence of retrosternal goiter reported in the literature varies widely (0.1–21%) with a mean of 10%; the incidence is around 1/5000 people and is more common in women than men with a female/male ratio of 4:1 [5,7] Retrosternal goiter tends to grow slowly and usually does not appear until the fifth or sixth decade of life [8].

Retrosternal goiter may remain asymptomatic for a long period of time and be discovered during routine radiological examinations due to other symptoms. The most common symptoms are due to the compressive effect of the mass on the trachea, resulting in symptoms ranging from mild cough, upper respiratory tract infection or dyspnea to severe, life-threatening stridor and asphyxia, as well as the impact on other nearby structures causing dysphagia, hoarseness and other neurological and vascular symptoms [2]. Clinical examination is not conclusive as in 20–30% of cases the goiter is not or barely palpable in the neck and the tumour is predominantly located in the chest [9].

X-rays of the neck and chest, computerized tomography [CT] and magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) are essential for diagnosis. Erbil and colleagues [10] reported that chest radiography can provide the first indication of substernal goiter in 77% of patients. Computed tomography has become the gold standard of preoperative radiological examination. It confirms the diagnosis and measures the size of the intrathoracic part of the goiter, which significantly influences the decision on the surgical procedure. MRI is helpful in visualizing the tissue and local invasion of the vascular structures by the mass. Fine needle aspiration biopsy for cytological analysis may be helpful in the presence of a cervical component, but is not usually recommended as it can be dangerous and the material obtained is often insufficient for histological diagnosis of malignancy [8].

Traditional anesthesiology warns of the difficult management of the airway in these patients. This is

thought to occur in all phases of anesthesia, including difficult bag and mask ventilation, difficult tracheal intubation, difficulties with positive pressure ventilation due to tracheal compression/deviation and postoperative problems due to tracheomalacia [11]. The incidence and extent of these problems is unclear and there has been considerable disagreement and lack of consensus on the occurrence of such complications and safe techniques to prevent and manage them. G. A. Dempsey et al [11] conducted a retrospective review of the anesthetic management of 34 patients undergoing thyroidectomy for retrosternal goiter at Aintree University Hospitals NHS Foundation. Nineteen patients had a massive retrosternal goiter extending to the aortic arch or beyond. All patients underwent tracheal intubation by direct laryngoscopy without problems, with only one case of failed intubation. Postoperative breathing problems or tracheomalacia did not occur. They suggest that in patients with massive retrosternal goiter undergoing thyroidectomy, intravenous induction of anesthesia and conventional direct laryngoscopy in appropriately experienced hands at a tertiary referral centre is a safe technique.

The conventional treatment for symptomatic retrosternal goiter is total thyroidectomy. Pressure symptoms due to retrosternal goiter such as dyspnea cough, stridor and dysphagia are considered absolute indications for surgery. The indications for surgery in asymptomatic patients are controversial. Many authors advocate surgery in all cases of retrosternal goiter, regardless of whether symptoms are present or not, due to the risk of airway obstruction, risk of malignancy, and the ineffectiveness of drug treatment with iodine-131 ablation and thyroxine suppression. [9].

Ideally, retrosternal goiter should be treated by a multidisciplinary team of specialists in endocrine surgery, thoracic surgery, endocrine medicine, radiology and anesthesiology, and surgical management should be planned preoperatively.

It is crucial to identify patients requiring sternotomy preoperatively in order to plan the need for a possible thoracotomy and to inform the patient correctly about the access that may be required.

Most retrosternal goiters can be removed by a standard collar incision. Only about 2% of patients may require a partial or complete thoracotomy [12]. Rugiu MG et al [13] retrospectively analyzed patients who underwent surgery for retrosternal goiter at the Department of Otorhinolaryngology of the University Hospital of Udine between 2004 and 2008. A total of 53 patients, 37 women and 16 men, were identified. Retrosternal goiters were removed via a cervical approach in 49 patients (92.5%); 4 patients (7.5%) required sternotomy because one patient had an ectopic thyroid gland in the

chest and the other 3 patients had a very large thyroid gland reaching the main bronchial bifurcation.

Various minimally invasive techniques have been proposed as alternatives to thoracotomy, including the trans clavicular approach described by D'Alia et al. (14), and minimally invasive video-assisted thoracoscopic surgery and da Vinci robotic surgery with the advantages of faster recovery and less morbidity.

Conclusion

Although retrosternal goiter has been an established clinical entity since 1749, it still poses some diagnostic and therapeutic difficulties. The respiratory symptoms caused by tracheal compression range from a mild cough to severe, life-threatening stridor. Computed tomography has become the gold standard for diagnosis. It confirms the diagnosis and is crucial for accurately grading the disease and predicting the likely surgical approach. Although surgery is agreed in all cases of retrosternal symptomatic patients, the indications for surgery in asymptomatic patients are still contradictory. Ideally, retrosternal goiter should be managed by a multidisciplinary team and it is crucial that patients requiring sternotomy are identified preoperatively to plan for the need for a possible thoracotomy and to correctly inform the patient of the approach that may be required. Most retrosternal goiters can be removed by a standard collar incision and only about 2 % require a thoracotomy. The trans clavicular approach and minimally invasive techniques such as video-assisted thoracoscopic surgery and da Vinci robotic surgery can replace the need for a thoracotomy with many advantages.

Conclusion Declaration

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